

Synthesizing copper tartrate crystals through controlled nucleation and growth in silica gel

D. V. Sonawane^a, R. R. Ahire

Dept. of Dept. of Physics, Jijamata Arts, Science Commerce College, Nandurbar.

Dept. of Physics, S.G.Patil College, Sakri Dist- Dhule, Maharashtra 424304

E-mail addresses : dvsonawane68@rediffmail.com(DVS),rr_ahire@yahho.co.in(RRA)

Abstract -Copper tartrate crystals were synthesized at room temperature using the single diffusion method within a sodium metasilicate gel matrix. Optimal growth conditions were determined by systematically varying parameters, including gel pH, density (concentration), and setting time, as well as the concentration of the reactants. The resulting crystals exhibited a characteristic bluish, opaque appearance.

Keywords-Silica gel, grown Copper tartrate crystals, bluish and opaque.

1 INTRODUCTION

Recent scientific advancements have shifted crystal analysis from traditional laboratory methods to sophisticated instrumental techniques that offer superior accuracy. While crystal growth was historically a subset of crystallography, it has evolved into an independent field driven by the need for high-purity materials unavailable in nature. Silica gel has emerged as an ideal, chemically inert medium for growing high-quality single crystals, providing a controlled environment for research and commercial applications.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 MATERIALS AND METHODS

Copper tartrate shows poor solubility in water hence it was thought worthwhile to grow such a kind of material by chemical reaction at controlled rate using gel method. Gel was prepared by using tartaric acid & sodium meta silicate . The chemicals use for the growth of

copper tartrate crystals; all chemicals were of AR grade. Take 7ml of tartaric acid (1M) in a small beaker. To tartaric acid add sodium metasilicate solution. (1M) drop by drop with constant stirring. Then the pH of solution maintains to 4 to 4.5, then pH is measured with digital pH meter.

Transfer the mixture in the borosilicate glass test tube in diameter is 2.5 cm & in length is 25 cm. Then cover its mouth with cotton plug. It is transparent initially, after 2/3 days, it turns into milky & gel converted into semisolid with little amount of water on the top of the surface which is called water of syneresis. Such gel cannot be used for reaction as it has not set. It vibrates with the small mechanical jerks allows the water of syneresis to evaporate completely. It may take one week & it does not vibrate with the small mechanical jerks i.e. called "Setting of gel".

After setting of gel, allow the aging of the gel. Aging makes gel the harder and reduces the diameter of the capillaries present in the gel. Take the copper chloride (CuCl_2) required concentration was then poured slowly along the sides of the test tube to avoid breaking of the gel. Copper chloride solution acted as upper reactants ions through the narrow pores of the silica gel leads to reaction between these ions and the ions present in the gel as lower reactant.[5-8].

The following reaction was expected inside the gel.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Crystals of copper tartrate are bluish opaque, diamond shaped. Maximum sizes of the grown crystals are 3mm x 4mm and thicknesses about 2 to 3mm are obtained.

1.Effect of gel density – It is observed that the nucleation density decreases with increases in gel density. Gels with high density sets more rapidly than the gels with low

density. Sodium meta silicate gel density 1.05gm/cm³. bluish ,dimond shaped crystals of copper tartrate.

2 Effect of conc of reaction –The volume of metasilicate gel required to adjust the pH value around 4.2 varies with conc.of tartaric acid . The good quality crystals were grown at 1M conc of tartaric acid.

3 Effet of conc of supernatant –copper chloride is used as supernatant with different conc. From 0.4to 1M is added around 70% of gel volume It is observed that 0.8M conc gives well defined crystals.

4 Effect of pH of gel - It is observed that As pH of gel increases the no. of crystals decreases due to contamination of crystal with gel In present work good quality crystals of copper tartarete were obtained at pH 4.2

5 Temperature – At normal temp

Different parameters such as concentration of reactants, pH of gel, impurities in the solvent, gel setting time, gel aging time, etc. have considerable effect on growth rate. Near gel interface dendrites growth is observed due to fast growth rate. However as the reactants percolates through the gel, the controlled reaction occurs below interface the depth of 3 to 4 cm. Hence good quality, bluish opaque crystals having well developed faces are observed. Optical micrograph of the grown crystal it shown fig. it shows bluish coloured & opaque crystal of copper tartrate Table 1 gives the various conditions for copper tartrate crystals grown in silica gel. Optimum condition of copper tartrate crystal Gel setting time

Table 1 Various optimum conditions for growing crystals were found

Various process parameter	Optimum conditions
Density of sodium meta silicate solution	1.05 g/cm ³
Concentration of tartaric acid	1 M
Volume of Tartaric acid	7 ml
Concentration Copper chloride	1 M
Volume of sodium meta silicate solution	18 ml

6 Effect of gel aging time – It was observed that as aging time of gel increased the number of crystals decreased gels were allowed to age for different period before about one week gives good quality crystals

Table no. 2-Effect of conc .of supernatant

Test Tube No.	SMS (1.05 g/cm ³)	Tartaric Acid(1M)	Conc.of Supernatant	Observation
1	18.3 ml	7ml	0.4M	Very few nucleation crystals; size is very small.
2	18.3ml	7ml	0.6M	Slight increase in crystal size compared to Tube 1.
3	18.2ml	7ml	0.8M	Optimal Results: Well-shining, isolated, bluish diamond-shaped crystals.
4	18.3ml	7ml	1.0M	Large number of crystals; multiple nucleation sites; not isolated.

In present work Figure 1 illustrates different morphologies of pure copper tartrate crystals different conditions of growth. Some bluish opaque crystals were observed. Figure 1 shows single bluish opaque crystal.

Fig. 1 shows insides the test tube copper crystal

4 CONCLUSIONS

The present investigation confirms that the gel growth technique is an effective and suitable method for the synthesis of high-quality copper tartrate crystals. It was observed that the crystal habit and morphology are highly sensitive to experimental parameters, specifically gel density, pH levels, and the concentration of the supernatant. Furthermore, preliminary characterization indicates that these copper tartrate crystals exhibit significant Non-Linear Optical (NLO) properties, suggesting potential applications in optoelectronic devices.

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